

1 **DelSIEVE: cell phylogeny modeling of single nucleotide variants**
2 **and deletions from single-cell DNA sequencing data**

3 **Supplementary notes**

4 Senbai Kang¹, Nico Borgsmüller^{2,3}, Monica Valecha^{4,5}, Magda Markowska^{1,6}, Jack Kuipers^{2,3}, Niko
5 Beerenwinkel^{2,3}, David Posada^{4,5,7}, and Ewa Szczurek^{8,1*}

6 ¹*Faculty of Mathematics, Informatics and Mechanics, University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland*

7 ²*Department of Biosystems Science and Engineering, ETH Zurich, 4058 Basel, Switzerland*

8 ³*SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, 4058 Basel, Switzerland*

9 ⁴*CINBIO, Universidade de Vigo, 36310 Vigo, Spain*

10 ⁵*Galicia Sur Health Research Institute (IIS Galicia Sur), SERGAS-UVIGO*

11 ⁶*Medical University of Warsaw, Postgraduate School of Molecular Medicine, Warsaw, Poland*

12 ⁷*Department of Biochemistry, Genetics, and Immunology, Universidade de Vigo, 36310 Vigo, Spain*

13 ⁸*Institute of AI for Health, Helmholtz Zentrum München, German Research Center for Environmental Health,*
14 *Neuherberg, Germany*

15 **Correspondence: ewa.szczurek@helmholtz-munich.de*

16 DelSIEVE model: continued

17 To model ADO mode using DelSIEVE, we introduce the corresponding prior distribution of α_{ij} ,
18 $P(\alpha_{ij} | g_{ij}, \theta_A)$, as defined in Additional file 3: Table S1, where θ_A denotes the allelic dropout
19 rate under the ADO mode. One should consider the “ADO occurred” column as the value
20 of an additional hidden random variable indicating the occurrence of an ADO, which will be
21 marginalized out in the model. For example, the probability of an ADO when $g_{ij} = 0/-$ equals
22 $\theta_A/2$, because there is only one allele left to be dropped out. For genotype $-$, it is certain that
23 ADO has not occurred as there is no allele existing.

24 To generalize DelSIEVE to model both ADO and LDO, we allow more than one allele to
25 drop out. $P(\alpha_{ij} | g_{ij}, \theta_L)$ is defined in Additional file 3: Table S2, where θ_L represents the
26 allelic dropout rate under the LDO mode. We assume that the ADOs occur to each allele
27 independently. For instance, when $g_{ij} = 0/0$, the probability of $\alpha_{ij} = 0$ is θ_L^2 , happening only
28 when both alleles drop out. For genotype $0/-$, the sole allele drops out with probability θ_L ,
29 resulting in zero sequenced alleles.

30 DelSIEVE likelihood

31 Combining the statistical phylogenetic model and the model of raw read counts described above,
32 the likelihood of the observed read count data under the DelSIEVE model becomes

$$P\left(\mathcal{D}^{(1)}, \mathcal{D}^{(2)} \mid \mathcal{T}, \beta, Q, h, \eta, t, v, \theta, f, w_1, w_2\right). \quad (\text{S.1})$$

33 To simplify notation, we denote some variables in the statistical phylogenetic model as
34 $\Theta = \{\mathcal{T}, \beta, Q, h, \eta\}$ and some in the model of raw read counts as $\Phi = \{t, v, \theta, f, w_1, w_2\}$. By
35 taking the logarithm, Equation (S.1) becomes

$$\log \mathcal{L}(\Theta, \Phi) = \log \mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\Theta, \Phi) + \log \mathcal{L}^{(2)}(\Theta, \Phi), \quad (\text{S.2})$$

36 where $\mathcal{L}^{(1)}$ is the tree likelihood corrected for acquisition bias computed for candidate SNV sites
37 in $\mathcal{D}^{(1)}$, while $\mathcal{L}^{(2)}$ is the likelihood computed for background sites in $\mathcal{D}^{(2)}$, referred to as the
38 background likelihood.

39 Acquisition bias in the context of phylogenetic reconstruction refers to the overestimation of
40 branch lengths (expected number of mutations per site) due to the use of only variable sites [49,

41 50]. Here, we correct for it following [51]:

$$\log \mathcal{L}^{(1)} = \log P \left(\mathcal{D}^{(1)} \mid \Theta, \Phi \right) + I' \log \left(\frac{1}{I} \sum_{i=1}^I C_i \right), \quad (\text{S.3})$$

42 where the first component is the uncorrected log-likelihood for SNV sites, and C_i in the second
43 component is the likelihood of SNV site i being invariant (see below).

44 To compute $\log P \left(\mathcal{D}^{(1)} \mid \Theta, \Phi \right)$ in [Equation \(S.3\)](#), we decompose it according to the prob-
45 abilistic graphical model in Figure 1b. Assuming independent and identical evolution of each
46 candidate variant site, $\log P \left(\mathcal{D}^{(1)} \mid \Theta, \Phi \right)$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \log P \left(\mathcal{D}^{(1)} \mid \Theta, \Phi \right) &= \sum_{i=1}^I \log \sum_{\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\}} \left[P \left(\mathcal{D}_i^{(1)} \mid \mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \Phi \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times P \left(\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\} \mid \Theta \right) \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I \log \sum_{\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\}} \left[\prod_{j=1}^J P \left(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \Phi \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times P \left(\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\} \mid \Theta \right) \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \log \sum_{\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\}} \left[P \left(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \Phi \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times P \left(\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\} \mid \Theta \right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.4})$$

47 where $P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \Phi)$, representing the model of raw read counts, is similarly decomposed
48 into

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \Phi) &= P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, f, w_{ij}, t, v, \theta) \\ &= \sum_{\alpha_{ij}, g'_{ij}} P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij}, \alpha_{ij}, g'_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, f, w_{ij}, t, v, \theta) \\ &= \sum_{\alpha_{ij}, g'_{ij}} \left[P(\mathbf{m}_{ij} \mid c_{ij}, g'_{ij}, f, w_{ij}) P(g'_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \alpha_{ij}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times P(c_{ij} \mid \alpha_{ij}, t, v) P(\alpha_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \theta) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.5})$$

49 $P(c_{ij} \mid \alpha_{ij}, t, v)$ in [Equation \(S.5\)](#) is defined through Equations (3)-(5), and $P(\mathbf{m}_{ij} \mid c_{ij}, g'_{ij}, f, w_{ij})$
50 is defined in Equation (11). Under the ADO mode, $P(\alpha_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \theta)$ and $P(g'_{ij} \mid g_{ij}, \alpha_{ij})$ are defined
51 as shown in Additional file 3: Table S1 and Table 1, respectively, while under the LDO mode in
52 Additional file 3: Table S2 and Table 2, respectively. As a result, [Equation \(S.5\)](#) takes distinct

53 forms under different dropout modes.

54 For the ADO mode, Equation (S.5) is further represented as

$$P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} | g_{ij}, \Phi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 P_{0/0} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta) \\
 \quad + P_{0/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot \theta, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 0/0, \\
 P_{0/1} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta) \\
 \quad + \frac{1}{2}(P_{0/-} + P_{1/-}) \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot \theta, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 0/1, \\
 P_{1/1} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta) \\
 \quad + P_{1/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot \theta, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 1/1, \\
 P_{1/1'} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta) \\
 \quad + P_{1/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot \theta, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 1/1', \\
 P_{0/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot (1 - \frac{\theta}{2}) \\
 \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \frac{\theta}{2}, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 0/-, \\
 P_{1/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot (1 - \frac{\theta}{2}) \\
 \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \frac{\theta}{2}, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 1/-, \\
 P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v), \text{ if } g_{ij} = -.
 \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S.6})$$

For the LDO mode, Equation (S.5) is

$$P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} | g_{ij}, \Phi) = \begin{cases} P_{0/0} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta)^2 \\ \quad + P_{0/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot 2 \cdot \theta \cdot (1 - \theta) \\ \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \theta^2, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 0/0, \\ P_{0/1} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta)^2 \\ \quad + (P_{0/-} + P_{1/-}) \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot \theta \cdot (1 - \theta) \\ \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \theta^2, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 0/1, \\ P_{1/1} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta)^2 \\ \quad + P_{1/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot 2 \cdot \theta \cdot (1 - \theta) \\ \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \theta^2, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 1/1, \\ P_{1/1'} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 2, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta)^2 \\ \quad + P_{1/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot 2 \cdot \theta \cdot (1 - \theta) \\ \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \theta^2, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 1/1', \\ P_{0/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta) \\ \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \theta, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 0/-, \\ P_{1/-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 1, t, v) \cdot (1 - \theta) \\ \quad + P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v) \cdot \theta, \text{ if } g_{ij} = 1/-, \\ P_{-} \cdot P(c_{ij} | \alpha_{ij} = 0, t, v), \text{ if } g_{ij} = -. \end{cases} \quad (\text{S.7})$$

Equation (S.4) is computed efficiently using Felsenstein's pruning algorithm [52]. For I candidate SNV sites, J cells and K genotype states in G (for DelSIEVE $K = 7$), the time complexity of the Felsenstein's pruning algorithm is $\mathcal{O}(IJK^2)$.

Since in the second component of Equation (S.3), C_i corresponds to the likelihood of candidate SNV site i being invariant, it is computed as the joint probability of \mathcal{D}_i and $\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)} = 0/0$:

$$\begin{aligned} C_i &= P\left(\mathcal{D}_i^{(1)}, \mathbf{g}_i^{(L)} = 0/0 \mid \Theta, \Phi\right) \\ &= P\left(\mathcal{D}_i^{(1)} \mid \mathbf{g}_i^{(L)} = 0/0, \Phi\right) \sum_{\mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\}} P\left(\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)} = 0/0, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\} \mid \Theta\right) \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^J P(\mathbf{m}_{ij}, c_{ij} | g_{ij} = 0/0, \Phi) \sum_{\mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\}} P\left(\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)} = 0/0, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\} \mid \Theta\right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.8})$$

61 which is computed similarly to Equation (S.4), but with g_{ij} for $j = 1, \dots, J$ fixed to 0/0. In fact,
 62 C_i and $\log P(\mathcal{D}_i^{(1)} \mid \Theta, \Phi)$ are computed simultaneously in the implementation for optimized
 63 efficiency.

64 To efficiently compute $\log \mathcal{L}^{(2)}$, the background likelihood in Equation (S.2), we make several
 65 simplifications similar to SIEVE. Specifically, we assume that each cell at each background
 66 site has the wildtype genotype and is sequenced without dropouts and with at least one read
 67 per allele. We also assume that $P(c_{ij} \mid \alpha_{ij}, t, v) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{g}_i^{(D)} = 0/0, \mathbf{g}_i^{(A)} \setminus \{g_{i(2J)}\} \mid \Theta) = 1$,
 68 thereby ignoring the model of sequencing coverage and the tree log-likelihood for the background
 69 sites i for $i = 1, \dots, I'$. With an alternative form of the Dirichlet-multinomial distribution, $\log \mathcal{L}^{(2)}$
 70 is approximately and efficiently computed by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log \mathcal{L}^{(2)}(f, w_1) &= \sum_{i=1}^{I'} \sum_{j=1}^J \log P_{0/0} \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^{I'} \sum_{j=1}^J \log \left[\frac{\Gamma(w_1) \Gamma(c_{ij} + 1)}{\Gamma(c_{ij} + w_1)} \prod_{k=1}^3 \frac{\Gamma(m_{ijk} + \frac{1}{3}fw_1)}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{3}fw_1) \Gamma(m_{ijk} + 1)} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \times \frac{\Gamma(c_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^3 m_{ijk} + (1-f)w_1)}{\Gamma((1-f)w_1) \Gamma(c_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^3 m_{ijk} + 1)} \right] \\
 &= I'J \left[\log \Gamma(w_1) - 3 \log \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{3}fw_1\right) - \log \Gamma((1-f)w_1) \right] \\
 &\quad + \sum_{c=1}^{\max(c_{ij})} N_c (\log \Gamma(c+1) - \log \Gamma(c+w_1)) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{k=1}^3 \sum_{m_k=1}^{\max(m_{ijk})} N_{m_k} \left(\log \Gamma\left(m_k + \frac{1}{3}fw_1\right) - \log \Gamma(m_k + 1) \right) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{c=\sum_{k=1}^3 m_k}^{\max(c_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^3 m_{ijk})} N_{c-\sum_{k=1}^3 m_k} \left(\log \Gamma\left(c - \sum_{k=1}^3 m_k + (1-f)w_1\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \log \Gamma\left(c - \sum_{k=1}^3 m_k + 1\right) \right), \tag{S.9}
 \end{aligned}$$

71 where $P_{0/0}$ is defined in Equation (11). Across I' background sites and J cells, N_c , N_{m_k} for $k =$
 72 $1, 2, 3$, and $N_{c-\sum_{k=1}^3 m_k}$ represent the unique occurrences of sequencing coverage c , of alternative
 73 nucleotide read counts m_k for $k = 1, 2, 3$, and of reference nucleotide read counts $c - \sum_{k=1}^3 m_k$,
 74 respectively. Some terms, namely $\log \Gamma(c+1)$, $-\log \Gamma(m_k + 1)$ for $k = 1, 2, 3$, and $-\log \Gamma(c -$
 75 $\sum_{k=1}^3 m_k + 1)$, are constants, and thus they are not updated in the MCMC iterations.

76 The time complexity of Equation (S.9) is $\mathcal{O}(c)$, where c is the number of unique values in the
 77 set of values representing sequencing coverage and read counts for all four nucleotides across I'

78 background sites and J cells. Since generally $IJK^2 \gg c$, the overall worst-case time complexity
 79 of model likelihood is $\mathcal{O}(IJK^2)$. It is worth noting that given I candidate variant sites and J
 80 cells, the time complexity of DelSIEVE is around three times greater than that of SIEVE due
 81 to the expanded genotype state space.

82 Priors

83 Similar to SIEVE, we use prior distributions predefined and implemented in BEAST 2 for some
 84 of the hidden random variables in the DelSIEVE model. For the cell phylogeny given by \mathcal{T}
 85 and β , we set a prior following the Kingman coalescent process with an exponentially growing
 86 population, denoted

$$P(\mathcal{T}, \beta | M, e), \tag{S.10}$$

87 where M and e are hidden random variables, representing the scaled population size and the
 88 exponential growth rate, respectively. The analytical form of Equation (S.10) is defined at length
 89 in [53].

90 The default assumed distribution for M in BEAST 2 is

$$P(M | \delta) = \frac{1}{\delta}, \tag{S.11}$$

91 where δ is the current proposed value of M .

92 As for e , the default prior is

$$e | \lambda, \epsilon \sim \text{Laplace}(\lambda, \epsilon), \tag{S.12}$$

93 where the default values of the fixed parameters are mean $\lambda = 10^{-3}$ and scale $\epsilon = 30.7$.

94 For η in Equation (1), an exponential prior distribution is chosen:

$$\eta | \gamma \sim \exp(\gamma), \tag{S.13}$$

95 where $\gamma = 1$.

96 For the relative deletion rate d , a uniform prior distribution is used:

$$d | \varphi \sim \text{Uniform}(0, \varphi), \tag{S.14}$$

97 where $\varphi = 1$.

98 For the hidden random variables in the model of sequencing coverage in Equations (3)-(5),
99 a non-informative prior is set for t :

$$t | \rho \sim \text{Uniform}(0, \rho), \quad (\text{S.15})$$

100 where $\rho = 1000$, while the prior for v is

$$v | \zeta \sim \exp(\zeta), \quad (\text{S.16})$$

101 where $\zeta = 25$.

102 For the allelic dropout rate θ_A defined under the ADO (Additional file 3: Table S1) or θ_L
103 under the LDO mode (Additional file 3: Table S2), we use a non-informative prior:

$$\theta | u \sim \text{Uniform}(0, u), \quad (\text{S.17})$$

104 where $u = 1$.

105 Regarding the hidden random variables in the model of nucleotide read counts in Equations
106 (7), (9) and (10), an exponential prior is set for f :

$$f | \tau \sim \exp(\tau), \quad (\text{S.18})$$

107 where $\tau = 0.025$, and a log normal prior for both w_1 and w_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} w_1 | \xi_1, \psi_1 &\sim \text{Log-Normal}(\xi_1, \psi_1), \\ w_2 | \xi_2, \psi_2 &\sim \text{Log-Normal}(\xi_2, \psi_2), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.19})$$

108 where we choose for w_1 the log-transformed mean $\xi_1 = 3.9$ (150 for untransformed) and the stan-
109 dard deviation $\psi_1 = 1.5$, and for w_2 the log-transformed mean $\xi_2 = 0.9$ (10 for untransformed)
110 and the standard deviation $\psi_2 = 1.7$. The mean is log-transformed using

$$\xi_{\text{transformed}} = \log(\xi_{\text{untransformed}}) - \frac{\psi^2}{2}.$$

111 These values of the fixed parameters in Equation (S.19) are chosen to cover a wide range of
112 possible values for w_1 and w_2 .

113 **Posterior and MCMC**

114 The posterior distribution of the hidden random variables is:

$$\begin{aligned}
& P\left(\mathcal{T}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, M, e, \eta, d, t, v, \theta, f, w_1, w_2 \mid \mathcal{D}^{(1)}, \mathcal{D}^{(2)}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{Z} P\left(\mathcal{D}^{(1)}, \mathcal{D}^{(2)} \mid \mathcal{T}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, Q, \eta, t, v, \theta, f, w_1, w_2\right) \\
&\quad \times P(\mathcal{T}, \boldsymbol{\beta} \mid M, e) P(M \mid \delta) P(e \mid \lambda, \epsilon) \\
&\quad \times P(\eta \mid \gamma) P(Q \mid d) P(d \mid \varphi) \\
&\quad \times P(t \mid \rho) P(v \mid \zeta) P(\theta \mid u) P(f \mid \tau) \\
&\quad \times P(w_1 \mid \xi_1, \psi_1) P(w_2 \mid \xi_2, \psi_2),
\end{aligned} \tag{S.20}$$

115 where $Z = P(\mathcal{D}^{(1)}, \mathcal{D}^{(2)})$ is a normalization constant, and the likelihood of the model and priors
116 for hidden random variables are defined in Section **DelSIEVE likelihood** and Section **Priors**,
117 respectively. To simplify the notation, we denote the hidden random variables in **Equation (S.20)**
118 as $\Lambda = \{\mathcal{T}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, M, e, \eta, d, t, v, \theta, f, w_1, w_2\}$.

119 Since Z in **Equation (S.20)** is intractable to calculate, we leverage BEAST2’s MCMC al-
120 gorithm with Metropolis-Hastings kernel to sample from the posterior distribution. In this
121 algorithm, a new state of the hidden random variables Λ^* is proposed based on its current state
122 Λ following a proposal distribution $q(\Lambda^* \mid \Lambda)$. $q(\Lambda^* \mid \Lambda)$ is designed to ensure the reversibility and
123 ergodicity of the underlying Markov chain. For DelSIEVE, in each iteration, a new state of a
124 randomly selected hidden variable is accepted with probability

$$\min \left\{ 1, \frac{P(\Lambda^* \mid \mathcal{D}^{(1)}, \mathcal{D}^{(2)}) q(\Lambda \mid \Lambda^*)}{P(\Lambda \mid \mathcal{D}^{(1)}, \mathcal{D}^{(2)}) q(\Lambda^* \mid \Lambda)} \right\}. \tag{S.21}$$

125 We employ exactly the same proposal distributions as in SIEVE. Briefly, regarding the branch
126 lengths of the tree, the heights of the internal nodes are adjusted. For the tree topology, we use
127 multiple moves, including subtree swapping, Wilson-Balding, and subtree sliding, where the last
128 two moves also change branch lengths as a side effect. With respect to unknown parameters,
129 scaling and random Gaussian walks are used. For detailed description of the aforementioned
130 moves, refer to Drummond *et al.* [53] and Kang *et al.* [32].

131 To achieve more accurate parameter and tree estimates, DelSIEVE employs a two-stage
132 sampling strategy similar to SIEVE.

133 Variant calling, dropout calling, and maximum likelihood gene annotation

134 In the computation of model likelihood using [Equations \(S.4\)](#) and [\(S.5\)](#), we marginalize out
135 some hidden random variables: $\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}$, $\mathbf{g}_i^{(A)}$, \mathbf{g}'_{ij} and α_{ij} . Hence, the direct results from the MCMC
136 sampling process are the posterior distributions of the cell phylogeny and other unknown hidden
137 random variables. We obtain the estimates of those marginalized hidden random variables in a
138 post-processing step. Specifically, we use the max-sum algorithm [54], by fixing the maximum
139 clade credibility tree [55] and parameters estimated from the MCMC posterior samples using
140 TreeAnnotator and Tracer [56], respectively. As a result, genotypes, dropout states, as well as
141 the locations of mutated genes on the inferred cell phylogeny are determined by identifying the
142 maximum likelihood states of $\mathbf{g}_i^{(L)}$, \mathbf{g}'_{ij} and α_{ij} , as well as $\mathbf{g}_i^{(A)}$, respectively.

143 ScDNA-seq data simulator

144 We generated simulated data by modifying the simulator we had used in Kang *et al.* [32]. The
145 simulator builds upon a previous simulation method, Cellcoal [57]. The first change we made
146 was to expand the rate matrix, according to which each genomic site evolved along the tree
147 (Additional file 3: Table S3). The rate matrix contains 14 genotypes encoded with nucleotides,
148 allowing for point mutations, back point mutations, and deletions. It has one parameter, the
149 deletion rate, which is measured relatively to the mutation rate. Another change was that we
150 implemented the LDO mode to allow more than one dropout to occur at each site for each cell.
151 The simulator takes the same input configuration as the simulator in Kang *et al.* [32] does.

152 The simulation process was similar to that in Kang *et al.* [32]. Briefly, with a given number
153 of cells, a binary cell lineage tree was first simulated following a neutral coalescent process with
154 exponential growth under a strict molecular clock, where the mutation rate is constant. For a
155 given number of genomic sites, each site was initialized by randomly selecting one of four nu-
156 cleotides to have a reference genotype. Next, with a given mutation rate and a relative deletion
157 rate, each site was evolved independently along the tree following the rate matrix defined in
158 Additional file 3: Table S3. A genomic site was considered as a true SNV site if at least one cell
159 had a genotype that was not wildtype. Dropouts were then added on top of the simulated geno-
160 types under either ADO or LDO mode, as long as there were non-deleted alleles. We recorded
161 the true dropout states for all cells at the true SNV sites. Size factors in Equation (6) were
162 generated from a normal distribution with the mean = 1.2 and the variance = 0.2. The sequenc-
163 ing coverage was simulated using a negative binomial distribution following Equations (3)-(5),

164 which closely followed our model assumptions. In order to break such association between model
165 assumption and data simulation, we made it optional to generate sequencing coverages following
166 the procedure originally implemented in CellCoal. The read counts of each nucleotide were then
167 generated following a multinomial distribution.

168 **Simulation design**

169 We designed a series of simulations to benchmark the performance of DelSIEVE. We reused and
170 modified the benchmarking framework we used for SIEVE.

171 **Simulations only considering SNVs**

172 We assumed that 40 tumor cells were sampled from an exponentially growing population, whose
173 growth rate and effective population size are 10^{-4} and 10^4 , respectively. We used the same
174 mutation rates as in the SIEVE benchmark, namely 10^{-6} , 8×10^{-6} and 3×10^{-5} . We selected
175 two relative deletion rates: 0.1 and 0.25.

176 For each mutation rate, we simulated a number of genomic sites such that the preselection
177 procedure would produce a certain amount of candidate variant sites, and additionally a high
178 enough number of background sites so that they provide signal for branch length correction. At
179 the same time, we kept the overall number of sites limited for computational efficiency reasons.
180 Specifically, for a mutation rate of 10^{-6} , we evolved 10^4 genomic sites to have around 400 ~ 700
181 candidate variant sites. For this simulated data, the resulting ratio of background to SNV sites
182 was around 5. For a mutation rate of 8×10^{-6} , 10^4 genomic sites were chosen to have around
183 4×10^3 background sites. For mutation rate 3×10^{-5} , 1.2×10^5 genomic sites were chosen to
184 have at least 2.5×10^3 background sites. For the higher mutation rates of 8×10^{-6} and 3×10^{-5} ,
185 the chosen numbers of genomic sites resulted in $> 5 \times 10^3$ and $> 1.1 \times 10^5$ true SNV sites,
186 respectively. Next, the obtained genomic sites were subsetted to ensure that the number of true
187 SNV sites in the final simulated data for different mutation rates were within the same range,
188 and that for the higher mutation rates 8×10^{-6} and 3×10^{-5} the ratio between the number of
189 background sites and the true SNV sites was kept similar to the data for the lowest mutation
190 rate (at least 5). To this end, we first computed a targeted number of true SNV sites for each
191 simulated dataset n_{target} using

$$n_{\text{target}} = \min(700, \frac{n'}{5}),$$

192 where n' is the number of background sites. Next, we randomly selected n_{target} sites out of
193 the true SNV sites. Together with the n' background sites, the selected n_{target} true SNV sites
194 formed the new simulated data.

195 We considered both ADO and LDO mode. The allelic dropout rate for the former was
196 $\theta_A = 0.3$, and for the latter $\theta_L = 0.163$ (both are the default setups in Cellcoal [57]).

197 We had different combinations of t and v in Equations (3)-(5) for various coverage qualities.
198 For simulated data referred to as high coverage quality, we used high mean ($t = 20$) and low
199 variance ($v = 2$) of allelic coverage. For medium coverage quality data, we used high mean
200 ($t = 20$) and medium variance ($v = 10$). For low coverage quality data, we fixed low mean
201 ($t = 5$) and high variance ($v = 20$).

202 Other parameters were fixed when simulating the data. We set w_1 and w_2 in Equation (10)
203 to 100 and 2.5, respectively. Moreover, we set both the amplification and sequencing error rate
204 to 10^{-3} , and thus the effective sequencing error rate in Equation (9) was $f \approx 2 \times 10^{-3}$.

205 Overall, we designed 36 simulation scenarios, each repeated 10 times.

206 Furthermore, for each of those genotypes related to deletions, we filtered out results if the
207 proportion of simulated ground truth was less than 0.1%. We also excluded results with a
208 mutation rate of 10^{-6} as too few deletions were generated (less than 0.3%, 0.7% and 0.005% for
209 alternative-left single deletion, reference-left single deletion and double deletions, respectively).
210 For the same reason, results were also excluded for double deletions with a mutation rate of
211 8×10^{-6} and for double mutant genotypes with a mutation rate of 10^{-6} , both of which had less
212 than 0.2% corresponding genotypes generated.

213 **Simulations considering SNVs, CNAs and doublets**

214 To simulate CNAs, we selected a specific simulation scenario described above with the following
215 parameters: 40 cells, medium mutation rate (8×10^{-6}), high relative deletion rate 0.25, medium
216 coverage quality ($t = 20$, $v = 10$), and single ADO mode ($\theta_A = 0.3$). We chose two levels of CNA
217 prevalence: $1/3$ and $2/3$ of all genomic sites. CNAs were then added using the same procedure as
218 described in Kang *et al.* [32], with the following modification regarding genotype adjustment.
219 If a site in a cell had only one allele before simulating CNAs, i.e., the genotype was originally
220 either 0/- (reference-remaining) or 1/- (alternative-remaining), amplifications would change the
221 underlying genotype to either 0/0 or 1/1, and deletions would remove the only allele, resulting
222 in double deletions genotype (-). If there were two alleles at a site in a cell, amplifications would

223 not change the underlying genotype, whereas deletions would accordingly.

224 To simulate doublets following the procedure described in the previous section, we selected
225 two levels of doublet rates: 0.02 and 0.1.

226 Additionally, we considered a particularly challenging simulation scenario, where a high
227 prevalence of CNAs ($\frac{2}{3}$ of all sites) and a high doublet rate (0.1) were added simultaneously.

228 Overall, we designed five simulation scenarios for CNAs and/or doublets, each repeated 10
229 times.

230 **Variant calling and phylogenetic accuracy**

231 For assessing the results of variant and dropout calling, standard performance measures such
232 as precision, recall, F1 score, and false positive rate (FPR) were used. These measures were
233 computed for DelSIEVE and SIEVE in the task of calling deletions as well as dropouts, and
234 computed for Monovar in addition to DelSIEVE and SIEVE in the task of calling single and
235 double mutant. Moreover, in order to compare to SCIPhIN, these measures were also computed
236 for DelSIEVE, SIEVE and Monovar with respect to the occurrence of deletions and/or single
237 and double mutant (see Section **Configurations of methods** in Additional file 1: Supplementary
238 notes). Note that, for the benchmark of genotype and single ADO calling in the presence of
239 doublets, we only considered singlets by excluding cells with doublets. The reason is that, since
240 DelSIEVE leverages the cell phylogeny to share information across all single cells, genotype
241 inference is implicitly interconnected among cells. Consequently, we aimed to evaluate whether
242 the presence of doublets indirectly affected the accuracy of genotype and single ADO inference
243 for singlets.

244 Both DelSIEVE and SCIPhIN identify deletions at preselected candidate sites. Hence, we
245 subsetted the true deletions to those at the candidate variant sites when computing the metrics.

246 To assess the accuracy of cell phylogeny reconstruction, we used the same measurements as
247 in Kang *et al.* [32], namely the BS distance [58] for both the tree topology and branch lengths,
248 as well as the normalized RF distance [59] for the tree topology only (see Kang *et al.* [32]). For
249 DelSIEVE, SIEVE and SiFit, we computed both the BS and the normalized RF distance in the
250 rooted tree mode. For SCIPhIN, we only computed the normalized RF distance as it only infers
251 a rooted tree without branch lengths. We used the R package phangorn to compute the BS and
252 normalized RF distances [60].

253 **Configurations of methods**

254 For Monovar (commit 68fbb68), we used the true values of θ and f as priors for the false negative
255 and false positive rates, and default values for other options.

256 For SCIPhIN (commit 27e5ca6), we gave it the true value of f to avoid estimating its mean
257 error rate (option “wildMean”), and ran it with 10^6 iterations with zygosity learned (option “lz”
258 set to 1). We also set the penalty of computing the loss (option “lp”) and parallel score (option
259 “lpp”) to 30. The command line was as follows:

```
260     sciphin -l 1000000 --lz 1 --ll 1 --lp 1 --llp 30 --lpp 30 --ese 0 \  
261     --wildMean 0.002
```

262 Note that SCIPhIN does not in its output differentiate deletions from SNVs; that is, it reports
263 both SNVs and deletions simply as mutations.

264 To run SiFit (commit 9dc3774), we fed the required data with variants called by Monovar
265 using a ternary matrix. We used the true values of θ and f as the prior for false negative rate
266 and the estimated false positive rate, respectively. We ran it with 2×10^5 iterations.

267 For SIEVE, originally it only supported ADO mode. To allow comparison to DelSIEVE in
268 LDO mode, we implemented LDO for SIEVE as well.

269 We enforced a strict molecular clock model for DelSIEVE and SIEVE, both of which were
270 run for 2×10^6 and 1.5×10^6 iterations for the first and the second sampling stages, respectively.
271 The deletion rate was inferred in the second sampling stage as it is related to the branch
272 lengths of the cell phylogeny. Both DelSIEVE and SIEVE were configured to match the dropout
273 mode (ADO or LDO) employed during the simulation process. Additionally, it is necessary to
274 evaluate the performance of DelSIEVE and SIEVE when their configured dropout modes are
275 distinct from that used to simulate a specific dataset. To this end, we selected the extremest
276 simulation scenarios for both the dropout modes (see Section [Simulation design](#) in Additional
277 file 1: Supplementary notes), namely the lowest and highest mutation rates (10^{-6} and 3×10^{-5} ,
278 respectively), the lowest and highest coverage qualities ($t = 20$, $v = 2$ and $t = 5$, $v = 20$,
279 respectively), and the highest relative deletion rate (0.25).

280 On the real datasets, we used a log-normal relaxed molecular clock model to account for
281 branch-wise substitution rate variation for DelSIEVE. To obtain better mixed Markov chains,
282 we used an optimized relaxed clock model [61] rather than the default one in BEAST 2. We
283 increased the number of iterations for both stages to 4×10^6 and 3.5×10^6 , respectively. Both

284 the deletion rate and parameters introduced by the relaxed molecular clock model were explored
285 in the second sampling stage. The first 10% of all samples were discarded for both sampling
286 stages to remove samples from the burn-in phase. As the simulation results showed that the
287 performance of DelSIEVE is not sensitive to the configured dropout mode, we applied DelSIEVE
288 in ADO mode to the real datasets. To evaluate the convergence of the DelSIEVE model, we ran
289 an additional MCMC chain for each real dataset using a different random seed and dispersed
290 initial values.

291 To run Ginkgo on the real datasets, sample bam files were first converted to bed files using
292 `bamtobed` function from `bedtools` (v2.28.0). With the bed files as input, we ran Ginkgo with
293 default settings, where hg19 reference genome, 1,000,000 bin size and `bwa` were used as the
294 aligner, and euclidian distance as the clustering option.

295 To run Sequenza on the real datasets, we used the `bam2seqz` command in the `sequenza-utils`
296 package to convert bam files for the corresponding bulk samples to the Sequenza file format,
297 which was subsequently binned with the `seqz-binning` command, using a window size of 50.
298 With this file as input, we used the `sequenza.fit` command from Sequenza v3.0.0 to estimate
299 the ploidy.

300 SNVs were annotated using Annovar (version 2020 Jun. 08) [62]. The cell phylogeny was
301 plotted in R (version 4.2.3) [63] using `ggtree` [64], and the genotype heatmap was plotted using
302 `ComplexHeatmap` [65]. Besides, the comparison of sequencing coverages reported by DelSIEVE
303 and Sequenza was performed and plotted using `ggstatsplot` [66].

304 Runtime analysis

305 For runtime analysis, we created two additional simulation scenarios with the following common
306 parameters: 100 cells, medium mutation rate (8×10^{-6}), high relative deletion rate (0.25),
307 medium coverage quality ($t = 20$, $v = 10$), and single ADO mode ($\theta_A = 0.3$). In the first
308 scenario, five replicate datasets were generated with a median number 798 of candidate variant
309 sites, while for the second scenario, another five replicates were simulated with a median number
310 1585 of candidate variant sites. Both stages of DelSIEVE and SIEVE were run for 10^5 iterations
311 under the default multithreading mode, with the same number of sites per thread.